

KUVA IS AN EXAMPLE OF EARLY MEDIEVAL URBAN CULTURE

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Annotation: *This article provides an overview of the history of archeological research in Kuva Shahrستان and the projects of a tourist destination being created in the area. The development of tourism in the region is expected to have a positive impact on other sectors.*

Keywords: *Kuva Shahrستان, archeology, Buddhism, tourism, Fergana, tourists, projects.*

Many historical and cultural heritage sites in our country serve our people and tourists around the world to gain a deeper understanding of history. Kuva Shahrستان, located in the Kuva district of Fergana region, is also a historically valuable monument. To better understand the historical significance of the object in the territory of Kuva Shahrستان, several archeological studies were conducted, and many residential buildings, objects and historical objects were found and studied.

In particular, in the early 30s of the XX century, during the construction of the Greater and Southern Fergana canals in 1939–1940 and in 1951 by members of the Pamir-Fergana archeological expedition, archeological excavations under the hills of Kuva Shahrستان left no doubt that the ruins of the ancient city were hidden.

The first large-scale excavations in ¹Kuva Shahrستان were started in 1956 by specialists at the Institute of History and Archeology under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Y.Gulyamov is the general director of this archeological research. With a break of 15 years, many archeological artifacts were found. At the entrance to the religious complex, which consists of a large rectangular courtyard (11.9x 11.9 m) and a temple (21 x 41 m) in the northern part of the city of Kuva, buried at a depth of only 40 cm above ground level.

²A Buddha statue twice the size of a lying human body was discovered during excavation. The Buddhist temple found during the excavations testifies to the fact that Buddhists lived in this part of the country. The findings of Kuva show the similarity of the materials found in India and East Turkestan, the development of cultural and economic ties in the Middle Ages, the rise of culture and art.³ The discovery of such archeological monuments shows how important the historical object of this region is. However, one of the most pressing issues today is to introduce this historical and

cultural heritage site to the world community and to meet the needs of tourists with infrastructure based on world standards.

A number of projects have been developed by the Fergana Regional Department of Cultural Heritage and the Fergana Regional Department of Tourism to turn cultural heritage sites into tourist attractions in the Fergana region.

In particular, there are plans to conduct large-scale work in the "Kuva Shahrستاني," which we are studying. that is, the establishment of the "Museum of Religions of the Fergana Valley," the entrance to the "Arch of the Qarakhanids" attached to the

¹ Heir Youth Magazine No. 6, 2011 Blessed Sources Secrets of the Kuva Valley A. Sodikov

² Heir Youth Magazine 2011, No.6 Buddhist Findings of Ancient Kuva Ph.D. N. Abdulhatov B. H. Matboboyev, R. T. Shamsutdinov, A.

³ Mamajonov and Ferganas cities on the Great Silk Road. Andijon: Meros, 1994. –P. 53.

defensive wall, the symbolic mausoleum "Ahmad al-Fargani," the construction of mint 7 billion soums, "Kuva Shahrستان 848.8 million soums for constructing 3.3 km bypass road, 600 million soums for electrification and lighting of new facilities, supply of drinking water, water supply and irrigation to new and existing facilities It is planned to allocate 584 million soums, a total of **9,032.8** billion soums.

⁴The implementation of this project will not only turn Kuva Shahrستان into a major tourist destination, but also have a positive impact on the lifestyle of the population of this region. Because of large-scale work, more than a hundred new jobs are expected to be created. Local entrepreneurs will also have the opportunity to expand and develop their industry-related activities.

In conclusion, it is important to preserve this place of our country, which has a rich historical past, in the best possible condition and pass it on to future generations, as well as to show that our country is one of the world's historical sites by attracting tourists is a task.

⁴ By the General Directorate of Tourism and Sports of Fergana region Report on the work done in January-September 2021 // Current archive. 2021